

Different land uses and regulations on the territory – case of Poland

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Abstract

The article aims at evaluating legal regulations on agricultural land to determine whether or not the regulations ensure that the land is used for agricultural purposes in Poland, especially as part of sustainable agriculture as well as for other purposes, i.e., afforestation, renewable energy and broadly defined development of rural areas (construction purposes, services, infrastructure). Additionally, the article analyses axiological grounds for actions taken by the Polish and the EU legislators in terms of agricultural land protection and using the land for different purposes. It also refers to applicable European Union documents, e.g. European Commission “farm to fork” strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system (F2F) of 20 May 2020, EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 called “Bringing nature back into our lives”.

The paper shows quantitative and qualitative instruments of agricultural land protection in Poland and the use of agricultural land and impact on biodiversity. Particular attention is drawn to Act of 11 April 2003 on the Formation of the Agricultural System and the Act on Agricultural and Forest Land protection of 3 February 1995. The Author concludes that in Poland there is an increasing number of regulations under which the owners and holders have obligations connected with the environmental protection, soil erosion protection, obligation to run an agricultural activity on agricultural land. Agricultural land tends to be more often dedicated for renewable energy investments which involve building and maintaining solar power plants or wind farms. The regulations and actions in Poland are in line with the European Green Deal.

Der Artikel setzt sich zum Ziel, die rechtlichen Regelungen für landwirtschaftliche Flächen zu bewerten, um festzustellen, ob die Regelungen sicherstellen, dass die Flächen in Polen für landwirtschaftliche Zwecke genutzt werden, insbesondere als Teil einer nachhaltigen Landwirtschaft sowie für andere Zwecke, d.h. Aufforstung, erneuerbare Energien und eine breit angelegte Entwicklung des ländlichen Raums (Bauzwecke, Dienstleistungen, Infrastruktur). Darüber hinaus analysiert der Artikel die axiologischen Gründe für die Maßnahmen des polnischen und des EU-Gesetzgebers in Bezug auf den Schutz landwirtschaftlicher Flächen und die Nutzung der Flächen für verschiedene Zwecke. Er bezieht sich auch auf einschlägige Dokumente der Europäischen Union, z.B. die Strategie der Europäischen Kommission für ein faires, gesundes und umweltfreundliches Lebensmittelsystem (F2F) vom 20. Mai 2020 und die EU-Strategie zur Erhaltung der biologischen Vielfalt bis 2030 mit dem Titel "Die Natur zurück in unser Leben bringen".

Der Beitrag zeigt die quantitativen und qualitativen Instrumente des landwirtschaftlichen Bodenschutzes in Polen sowie die Nutzung landwirtschaftlicher Flächen und deren Auswirkungen auf die biologische Vielfalt. Besonderes Augenmerk wird auf das Gesetz vom 11. April 2003 über die Gestaltung des Agrarsystems und das Gesetz über den Schutz landwirtschaftlicher und forstwirtschaftlicher Flächen vom 3. Februar 1995 gelegt. Die Autorin kommt zu dem Schluss, dass es in Polen eine wachsende Zahl von Vorschriften gibt, die den Eigentümern und Besitzern Verpflichtungen im Zusammenhang mit dem Umweltschutz, dem Schutz vor Bodenerosion und der Verpflichtung zur Ausübung einer landwirtschaftlichen Tätigkeit auf landwirtschaftlichen Flächen auferlegen. Landwirtschaftliche Flächen wer-

den tendenziell häufiger für Investitionen in erneuerbare Energien genutzt, die den Bau und die Instandhaltung von Solarkraftwerken oder Windparks beinhalten. Die Vorschriften und Maßnahmen in Polen stehen im Einklang mit dem europäischen Green Deal.

1. Introduction

Land is used for different purposes, such as agriculture, forestry, renewable energy, housing or business activity (van Vliet, et al., 2020). In Poland, agricultural land accounts for more than 60% of the area, including 45% of arable land. Unfortunately, 34% of that land is of 5th and 6th class valuation, which means it is of a poor quality and gives not enough crops. More than 25% of soil is at risk of wind erosion and 28% - of water erosion (Ministry of the Environment, 2016). A vital issue is restoration of degraded and destroyed land by bringing back its natural or practical significance (Ministry of the Environment, 2016).

The soil formation modification process has been deeply contributed by human activity, including business, agricultural and other types of activity. The analyses in the article focus, most of all, on agricultural land used for agricultural purposes. Agricultural land is of high importance for the food production and environmental protection.

Under the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019) the importance of soils in the biodiversity strategy, farm to fork and climate law has been specified. In all three policies, greater soil protection is to be achieved by 2030 by the following means: 50% reduction of pesticides, 50% reduction of excess nutrients, 20% reduction of fertilizers, organic farming on 25% of agricultural land, 10% increase in landscape of the feature, increase of protected areas by 30%, restoration of wetlands and stopping soil degradation (Montanarella & Panagos, 2021).

The EU legislator also brings to the table the opportunity to use low-quality agricultural land for afforestation purposes. The increasing amount of agricultural land is used for the renewable energy purposes such as, inter alia, wind farms or photovoltaics. Some smaller plots, especially those up to 1 hectare, are used for the housing purposes or business activity purposes. Land is used for the development of rural areas.

It needs to be pointed out that the Polish Act of 2003 on the Formation of Agricultural System lays down the goals which are similar to those provided for in the EU documents. The Act has been enacted "to ensure proper management of agricultural land in the Republic of Poland, to *guarantee food security of the citizens and to support sustainable agriculture run in compliance with the environmental protection requirements and facilitate the development of rural areas*".

The article aims at evaluating legal regulations on agricultural land to determine whether or not the regulations ensure that the land is used for agricultural purposes in Poland, especially as part of sustainable agriculture as well as for other purposes, i.e., afforestation, renewable energy and broadly defined development of rural areas (construction purposes, services, infrastructure). Additionally, the article analyses axiological grounds for actions taken by the Polish and the EU legislators in terms of agricultural land protection (Consolidated text: Journal of Laws of 2020, item 1655) and using the land for different purposes. It also refers to applicable European Union documents.

2. Land protection in current EU documents and policy

The European Union has been currently working on the execution of the European Commission “farm to fork” strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system (F2F) of 20 May 2020 (European Commission, 2020; Montanarella & Panagos, 2021). The aim of this document is to bring about a holistic change in the approach to food production. It indicates that the food chain should have a neutral or positive impact on the environment and it also focuses on ensuring food safety, nutrition safety and public health, as well as preserving the affordability of food. The strategy underlines that the COVID-19 pandemic, the increasing incidence of droughts, floods, forest fires and new pests, is a reminder that the food system is under threat and must become more sustainable and resilient (European Commission, 2020; Montanarella & Panagos, 2021). There is an urgent need to reduce dependency on pesticides, reduce excess fertilisation, increase organic farming, improve animal welfare, and reverse biodiversity loss. That is why it is of such high importance to use land for agricultural purposes.

Under the European Commission “farm to fork” strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system (F2F) of 20 May 2020 (European Commission, 2020), the farmers cultivating agricultural land need to transform their production methods more quickly, and make the best use of nature-based, technological, digital, and space-based solutions to deliver better climate and environmental results, increase climate resilience and reduce and optimise the use of inputs (e.g. pesticides, fertilisers).

In March 2020, the European Commission also proposed the first European Climate Law (EU Climate Law, 2020) to achieve a climate-neutral EU by 2050 (as part of the European Green Deal). With regard to soil, this ambitious plan involves maintaining wetlands as an important carbon sink and reducing CO₂ emissions in the agricultural sector. In addition, the Commission is to adopt an Action Plan for Zero Air, Water and Soil Pollution in 2021, Soils and agriculture (Montanarella & Panagos, 2021).

Using agricultural land for the purpose of agriculture and environmental protection fits into the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 called “*Bringing nature back into our lives*”. It was published by the European Commission on 20 May 2020. As far as biodiversity (EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 called “*Bringing nature back to our lives*” was published by the European Commission on 20 May 2020. The Strategy envisages the restoration of biological diversity of Europe with the benefit for people, climate and the planet; (European Commission, 2020) is concerned, the European Commission suggests that 10% of agricultural land needs to consist of high-diversity landscape features, for instance in the form of hedges or buffer strips, and recommends substantial reduction of the impact of the agricultural sector on the environment by 2030. A quarter of agricultural land needs to be managed for organic farming (ibidem) by the year 2030 (Montanarella & Panagos, 2021).

Unfortunately, soil degradation is a common, systemic process present in all parts of the world and it can take many forms in the EU and worldwide (Gilbey, et al., 2019, pp. 230-237). Tackling soil degradation and restoring degraded land is an urgent priority for the protection of biodiversity and ecosystem services. Various soil degradation (farming, soil contamination, compaction, soil sealing, organic carbon decline), climate changes and intensive exploration by a person endangered by microorganisms require the introduction of Sustainable Soil Management (SSM). Such system can bring many environmental benefits and funding sources (Lugato E., 2014, pp. 3557-3567).

Sustainable soil management was defined in 2016 by FAO in Voluntary Guidelines for Sustainable Soil Management Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2017, p. 4 et seq.). All FAO members, including EU Member States and the European Commission, endorsed those guidelines that intended to minimize soil erosion, foster soil nutrient balance and cycles, prevent and minimize soil contamination and soil acidification, preserve and enhance soil biodiversity, prevent and mitigate soil compaction, improve soil water management.

3. Quantitative and qualitative instruments of agricultural land protection in Poland. The use of agricultural land and impact on biodiversity

It needs to be pointed out that owing to their natural qualities and inevitable process of the depletion of their resources, agricultural land constitutes valuable national good (Stempka C., 1979, p. 107). It cannot be replaced with any other production means and, therefore, it needs to be prevented from being “worn out” (Błażejczyk, 1967, pp. 78-100; Wróbel, 1984, pp. 8-16). The soil is one of the most complex ecosystems there are and it is a highly crucial non-renewable resource of a high significance for human health as well as for the production of food and medicine (European Environment Agency, 2019).

Therefore, it is essential to take actions to protect soil fertility, prevent soil erosion and increase the amount of soil organic matter. To achieve that the sustainable development practices, also within the Common Agricultural Policy (mission in soil health and food carried out as part of “Horizon Europe”, European Commission, 2020), need to be adopted. The consequences of soil erosion and depletion of organic carbon in soil are getting more and more apparent. Desertification is yet another threat in the EU which is growing in significance (European Court of Auditors, 2018). Additionally, the Resolution of the European Parliament of 27 April 2017 on the state of play of farmland concentration in the EU: how to facilitate the access to land for farmers, emphasizes that whereas land is on the one hand property, on the other – it is a public asset and is subject to social obligations. The Resolution also points out that land is a finite, increasingly scarce resource and it constitutes the basis of the human right to healthy and sufficient food as well as of many ecosystem services vital to survival. Thus, the document rightly concludes that agricultural real property should not be treated as an ordinary item of merchandise (European Parliament, 2016).

Sustainable agriculture aims at promoting a sustainable management system. In general, based on its broader interpretation, sustainable agriculture is about rational management of natural resources, which allows for reducing a negative impact of agriculture on the environment and prevents the depletion of organic substance in soil (ARiMR, 2015). Sustainable agriculture, in its broad meaning, assumes running an agricultural activity in a socially responsible way (Polskie Stowarzyszenie Rolnictwa Zrównoważonego „ASAP”, 2014).

There are instruments of quantitative and qualitative protection of agricultural land in Poland that need to be noted. They are included in various legal acts. Most of all, it is the Act on the Formation of Agricultural System that needs to be mentioned. Consequently, the Polish law makers strive to provide for instruments which are to protect the real estate. Pursuant to Article 23 of the Constitution of the

Republic of Poland, the agricultural regime in our country is grounded in family holdings, and this constitutional principle is respected in contracts of the purchase of agricultural real estate.

On 16 July 2003, the Act of 11 April 2003 on the Formation of the Agricultural System (Consolidated text: Journal of Laws of 2018, Item 1405, 1496, 1637, as amended) came into force in Poland. As a rule, the legislator introduces legal instruments supporting the development of family farms run by individual farmers. As it has already been indicated, agricultural properties are purchased, most of all by persons who have agricultural qualifications and if the area of agricultural land does not exceed 300 ha (Suchoń, 2017).

Agricultural property can be purchased only by an individual farmer (a family farming holding, in turn, is a unit run by an individual farmer, that is a natural person who is an owner, perpetual usufruct, autonomous possessor or lessee of agricultural real property whose combined area of arable land does not exceed 300 hectares, who holds agricultural qualifications and has been residing for a period of at least 5 years in the commune in whose territory at least one of the agricultural real properties forming part of the farming holding is located, and who has been running this farm personally throughout this period), unless the act specifies otherwise. The act specified that the rule (an agricultural real estate can be purchased only by an individual farmer) does not apply to, for example, next of kin, territorial self-government units, State Treasury or the Agricultural Property Agency (now National Support Centre for Agriculture) acting on its behalf, legal entities acting on the basis of provisions on the relationship between the State and the Catholic Church in the Republic of Poland, on the relationship between the State and other churches and religious associations and on guarantees of the freedom of conscience and religion, national parks (in the event of the purchase of agricultural real property for purposes in connection with the protection of the natural environment). At the same time, the provisions provide for some exceptions allowing the acquisition of agricultural property based on permits issued by the National Support Centre for Agriculture: at the application of the seller or buyer upon the satisfaction of statutory prerequisites. One of the conditions allowing for the use of agricultural land is going to be the obligation to run agricultural activity on that land. The acquirer of the agricultural property is obliged to run the farming holding whose part is the acquired agricultural property for a period of at least 5 years from the acquisition of that property, and in the case of natural persons - to run it personally (Blajer, 2020). Throughout that period, the acquired property may not be disposed of nor given for possession to other entities, at the application of the acquirer of agricultural property, will issue a permit for such transaction prior to the lapse of 5 years from the transfer of ownership of that property if it is necessary due to unforeseen circumstances outside of the control of the acquirer.

It needs to be clarified that an agricultural farm is a unit where the area of agricultural real estate or a total area of real estates is not smaller than 1 hectare.

What needs to be emphasized is that in the period from 30 April 2016 to 25 June 2019, the agricultural activity had to be run on agricultural real estates for 10 years from the time of their purchase. Currently, that obligation amounts to 5 years but it has been extended and covers close relatives who acquired land under the contract of sale, donation or other type of a contract (Suchoń, 2019, pp. 91-111).

The real estate can be purchased by other entity than an individual farmer if the real estate is smaller than 1 hectare, as a result of dissolution of co-ownership, division of common estate after the dissolution of marriage and division of the estate; as a result of division, transformation or merger of commercial-law companies. In such a case, however, the National Support Centre for Agriculture has the right of pre-emption or the right to purchase the real estate in question. The right of pre-emption and the right of buyout of National Support Centre for Agriculture does not apply if, most of all, as a result of purchasing a family farm gets enlarged to a surface area not bigger than 300 hectares and the purchased real estate is located in the commune where the purchaser resides or in the neighbouring commune.

The land below 1 hectare is often purchased so that it can be used for housing or business activity purposes, which fits into the development of rural areas. That term is broadly defined in the EU legislation. Its main goals include diversifying rural economy and enhancing the quality of life in rural areas by providing better access to employment, public goods and services and, at the same time, by reducing unfavourable processes. Not sufficient infrastructure and poor access to public services in rural areas result from lower investment level and lack of entrepreneurship in reference books there is also a term “vitality of agricultural land”, which refers to jobs, minimum level of services and infrastructure as well as to human potential, good social networks, attractiveness of rural areas as a place to live, work and visit. Lands, landscape features, climate and other natural factors collectively contribute to the way customs, traditions and identity of rural areas are shaped. (Baldock, et al., 2010).

Apart from the Act on the Formation of the System, there is also the Act on Agricultural and Forest Land protection of 3 February 1995 (Consolidated text: Journal of Laws of 2017, Item 1161, as amended), which provides for instruments of quantitative and qualitative protection of agricultural land. It can be exemplified by the procedure of changing the status of agricultural land into a non-agricultural one. First, the spatial development plan is modified and, then, land gets excluded from agricultural production. As a rule, excluding land from the production entails fees. As for the best 1st-3rd class valuation, the fees are high and the permission of the Ministry of Agriculture is needed. There are a number of instruments connected with qualitative protection of agricultural land. A general rule is that Article 15 of the Act on Agricultural and Forest Land protection indicates that the owner of land constituting agricultural land and land restored for agricultural purposes is obliged to take actions preventing the soil degradation, especially erosion and soil mass movements.

There are EU schemes relating to environment protection dedicated for agricultural land owners that need to be mentioned. Article 9 of Act of 5 February 2015 on payments under direct payments (Journal of Laws of 2015, Item 308 as amended) specifies that a farmer is obliged, under Article 43(1) of Regulation No 1307/2013, to comply with the practices referred to in that Article: Article 43 prescribes that, on all their eligible hectares, farmers entitled to a payment under the basic payment scheme or the single area scheme must observe agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and environment referred to in (3) of that Article. The agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment are the following: a) crop diversification; b) maintaining existing permanent grassland; and c) having ecological focus area on the agricultural area.

The regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 18 March 2015 on detailed conditions and procedure for granting financial aid under “Agricultural, environmental and climatic action” measure covered by the 2014–2020 Rural Development Programme (Journal of Laws of 2015,

Item 415 as amended) specifies that agricultural, environmental and climatic action is executed as part of: one package (if a package does not include an alternative) or an alternative, e.g. Sustainable agriculture; Soil and waters protection: Maintaining orchard and traditional types of fruit trees: Precious habitats and endangered species of birds in the areas of Natura 2000: Preserving endangered genetic resources of plants in agriculture – in the event of crops; maintaining endangered genetic resources of animals in agriculture.

A farmer has environmental and climatic obligation: has an agri-environmental activity plan, is not allowed to transform grassland or feedland that is included in the agricultural farm, preserves, existing in an agricultural farm, elements of agricultural landscape which are not used for agricultural purposes but they create nature refuges, specified in the plan of agri-environmental activity. By executing the above-mentioned activities, they contribute to the protection of the environment and biodiversity.

It needs to be highlighted that grassland and feedland have been, for centuries, genuine oasis of biodiversity, rich in various types of plants and animals (Kujawsko-Pomorski Ośrodek Doradztwa Rolniczego w Minikowie, 2017). In Poland, grassland and feedland, namely so-called permanent grassland accounts for about 12% of the surface area of the country (about 3 million hectares), and about 8% in the whole European Union (57 million hectares). Intensive cultivation of grassland and feedland (instead of extensive one), large amounts of artificial fertilizers, herbicides and early harvesting leave numerous types of birds stranded for food, destroy their nests and harm their cubs (Kujawsko-Pomorski Ośrodek Doradztwa Rolniczego w Minikowie, 2017). Permanent grassland consumes almost as much carbon dioxide as forests. Agriculture can play a significant part in reducing greenhouse gases that it generates. Removing part of cumulated CO₂ from the atmosphere is of high importance for stabilizing global climate (European Commission, 2010).

It needs to be highlighted that biological diversity in soil is higher than above it. Soil is home to more than a quarter of all species on earth. Humus cannot be produced in an artificial way as it is created by biological diversity of soil (Feledyn-Szewczyk, 2014), sustainable, ecological and integrated agriculture (Feledyn-Szewczyk, 2014). It is possible to distinguish the concept of protection of biodiversity of agroecosystems “land sharing”, i.e., running in one area an agricultural activity of low intensity that ensures the protection of the resources of the environment (Feledyn-Szewczyk, 2014). On the other hand, there is a concept called “land sparing” – splitting the areas that are intensively used for agricultural purposes from natural or partially natural habitats which constitute diversity reservoir (Feledyn-Szewczyk, 2014).

4. Agricultural land afforestation

The regulations incentivize to dedicate agricultural land of poor valuation for afforestation. Forest land, because of its plants, constitutes a highly crucial element of the environment, helping to improve the quality of air, giving shelter to many animals and contributing to leisure activities of people. As it is highlighted, it has got a favourable impact on climate, soil, water, living conditions and human health as well as biological balance (Radecki, et al., 2016, p. 25 et seq.). In 2019, the area of forest land in Poland amounted to 9 462,9 hectares, including forests of an area of 9 258,8 hectares, which accounted for 29,6% of the area of Poland. Compared with 2018, there was an increase in the area of forests by almost 4 thousand hectares, which resulted from afforestation of non-forest land used for agricultural purposes or of wasteland. In 2019, public forests accounted for 80,7% of total area of

forests (76,9% of total area of forests was managed by the National Forests). Private forests area was 1 787 hectares (19,3% of forests in the country), including more than 94% of those owned by natural persons (18,2% of forests in total) (GUS, 2019).

Article 14 of the Act on Forests specifies that forest resources can be enlarged by land afforestation and enhancing forest productivity in a manner regulated in the forest management plan. Afforestation can be performed on wasteland, agricultural land useless for agricultural production and agricultural land not used for agricultural purposes and other types of land suitable for afforestation, in particular: 1) land located near rivers and spring water heads, on watersheds, along river banks as well as on the perimeter of lake and water reservoirs; 2) quicksand and sandy dunes; 3) steep slopes, hillsides, bluffs and subsidence; 4) spoil heaps and areas where sand, gravel, peat and clay used to be located.

Agricultural land afforestation is incentivized by the EU schemes. Both Polish and the EU (Tomkiewicz, 1999, p. 72 et seq.) legislators make attempts to support the land afforestation process by implementing financial instruments incentivizing to assign land to afforestation areas. Even before Poland's accession to the EU, the Act of 8 June 2001 on Agricultural Land Afforestation (Journal of Laws of 2001, No 73, Item 764, as amended) was adopted. Under the Act, agricultural land which was part of an agricultural farm or made the farm on its own could be dedicated for afforestation if it fulfilled at least one from the below-mentioned conditions: was a land 1) of 6th z, 6th and 5th class as well as the 4th class if its area does not exceed 10% of total area of land dedicated for afforestation, 2) located on the average slope above 15%, 3) degraded within the meaning of Act of 3 February 1995 on Protection of Agricultural and Forest Land (and if it is intended for afforestation in the local spatial development plan or decisions of land development).

Following Poland's accession to the European Union, the issue of afforestation was regulated in Regulation of the Council of Ministers of 11 August 2004 on detailed conditions and procedure for granting financial aid for afforestation of agricultural land under the Rural Development Programme (Journal of Laws of 2004, No 187, Item 1929, as amended). Pursuant to that regulation, payment for afforestation shall be granted to an agricultural producer who is a natural person or an agricultural production cooperative and undertakes, among other things, to afforest agricultural plots on which, until the date of applying for payment, agricultural activity had been run, maintain an afforestation area for the period of 5 years from the date of the afforestation – in compliance with the afforestation plan, within the meaning of the regulations on forests; run created afforestation areas for the period of 20 years from the date of being granted the first afforestation payment.

In another regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 19 March 2009 on detailed conditions and procedure for granting financial aid under "Afforestation on agricultural lands and afforestation of non-agricultural lands" measure covered by 2007-2013 Rural Development Programme (Journal of Laws of 2009, No 48, Item 390, as amended), aid for afforestation was granted not only for agricultural land but also for non-agricultural one. According to the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 8 May 2015 on detailed conditions and procedure for granting aid under "Investments in the development of forest areas and the improvement of forest viability" measure covered by 2014-2020 Rural Development Programme (Journal of Laws of 2015, Item 655, as amended) aid is granted to the farmer who undertakes, among other things, to: perform

afforestation of land in compliance with the afforestation plan requirements, maintaining afforestation on the land referred to for the period of 12 years from the date of applying for the first afforestation bonus – in the event of applying for the afforestation bonus (Suchoń, 2018, pp. 207-227).

Currently, this is the Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development of 26 March 2019 on detailed conditions and procedure for granting financial aid under “Support for afforestation and creating afforested areas” measure covered by 2014-2020 Rural Development Programme that is in force. A farmer is granted aid pursuant to Article 4(1) letter a of the Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council (EU) No 1307/2013 of 17 December 2013 establishing rules for direct payments to farmers under support schemes within the framework of the common agricultural policy, if: among other things, they were granted an identification number under regulations on the national system of keeping register of producers, register of agricultural farms and register of payment applications, that can be used while applying for that aid.

Additionally, the farmer undertakes to: a) perform land afforestation in compliance with the afforestation plan requirements referred to in Article 35(5) point 1 of the Act of 28 September 1991 on Forests, hereinafter referred to as “Afforestation Plan” and, if specified in the afforestation plan, to make a fence or secure trees with 3 pegs – in the event of applying for afforestation aid, b) maintain the afforestation performed on land referred to in letter a, or the afforestation that took place on the land as a result of natural succession, in compliance with the afforestation plan requirements, for the period of 5 years from the date of applying for the first maintenance bonus – in the event of applying for the maintenance bonus, c) keep afforestation on the land referred to in a) for the period of 12 years from the date of applying for the first afforestation bonus – in the event of applying for the afforestation bonus; 3) got a decision on the environmental constraints for the afforestation plan – in the event of applying for afforestation support and if the planned afforestation is a project the execution of which requires getting such a decision pursuant to Act of 3 October 2008 on Sharing Information about the Environment and its Protection, Public Participation in Environmental Protection and Environmental Impact (Journal of Laws of 2018, Item 2081). The farmer is granted aid in connection with land: 1) included in the land and buildings register pursuant to Article 2 point 8 of the Act of 17 May 1989 on Geodetic and Cartographic Law (Journal of Laws 2017, Item 2101 and of 2018, Item 650 and 1669) as agricultural land; 2) constituting arable land or an orchard; 3) which was dedicated for afforestation in the local spatial development plan and if there is no such plan, if afforestation of such land does not go against the land use plan of a commune and, if there is neither afforestation plan nor land use plan – if the land has been dedicated for afforestation under a land development conditions decision.

RDP 2007–2013 afforestation covered 36.763,15 hectares, including 2008 – 6.405,97 hectares; 2010 – 6.142,17 hectares; 2011 – 6.166,45; 2012 – 5.646,34; 2013 – 4.672,45; 2014 – 2.409,83 hectares; 2015 – 1.299,79 hectares (GUS, 2016, p. 86 et seq.). The area of afforested agricultural land and wasteland in 2019 amounted to 1 164,5 hectares and was more than 156 hectares lower compared with 2018 (decrease by 12%). 59 hectares qualified as natural succession (in 2018 – 69 ha). Owners of private forests accounted for 66,1% of total afforestation in 2019, while the State Forest – for 29,7% (GUS, 2019, p. 31 et. seq.).

It needs to be pointed out that, under the Act on the Protection of Agricultural and Forest Land, the starost is allowed, due to soil protection against erosion and earth mass movements, by means of

decision, to order the agricultural land owner, to perform afforestation, tree planting or shrub planting of land or creating permanent grassland on it. The land owner is entitled to be reimbursed for the costs of necessary seeds and seedlings from the budget of a province (Article 15 of the Act).

5. Using agricultural land for renewable energy purposes

In recent years there has been a tendency to make agricultural land available for the purposes of building and maintaining a solar power plant or a wind farm (Gram w zielone, 2020). One of priorities of that strategy is that by 2020 Poland will have had at least 15% share of renewable energy sources in final energy consumption gross, including at least 10% share of renewable energy used in transport (Suchoń, 2015, pp. 313-321). The obligation to achieve the above-mentioned goal results directly from the Directive 2009/28/EC on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources and amending and subsequently repealing Directives 2001/177/EC and 2003/30/EC (Official Journal of the European Union L 140/16). It goes without saying that in order to achieve these indicators it is necessary to adopt acts favourable for the development of that sector as well as to ensure fast and effective implementation of renewable energy projects. Currently in Poland, the main act regulating the issue of renewable energy is the Act of 20 February 2015 on renewable energy sources (Journal of Laws of 2020, Item 261, 284, 568, 695, 1086, 1503) and Act of 10 April 1997 on Energy Law (Journal of Laws of 2020, Item 833, 843, 875, 1086, 1378, 1565).

The contracts regulating renewable energy projects on agricultural land have various names: real estate lease contract or contract for using land for renewable energy purposes. It is worth explaining that the Supreme Court in its decision of 5 October 2012 (IV CSK 244/12) ruled that *the contract providing a party with the right to generate income from the sales of electric energy obtained from processing wind energy by means of wind turbines in turn for periodical monetary benefit defined as the percentage from the value of sold electric energy is an innominate contract to which, to the matters not regulated in such a contract, provisions of the civil code on lease can apply* (Suchoń, 2015, pp. 313-321). The limited scope of the article does not allow to refer to that decision. Many specialists in the subject, however, do not agree with the decision of the Supreme Court, which is exemplified by, among other things, the gloss to the above-mentioned decision by Ł.M. Wyszomirski (Wyszomirski, 2013).

Undoubtedly, it is less time-consuming and much easier to carry out solar power plant investments in terms of legal and construction aspects than wind power plant investments. If there is no spatial development plan in a given commune, agricultural land is allowed to be used for investment after obtaining a decision on land development and management conditions. Execution of such investments entails excluding agricultural land from agricultural production. The contracts are usually concluded for the period of 25 years. Power of photovoltaic power plants in Poland as of the end of July amounted to 2261,3 MW, increasing in the first seven months of this year by 961,7 MW (Gram w zielone, 2020). In 2019, 3,5-fold more photovoltaic installations were put to use that a year before (Macuk, 2020). Despite a fast increase in power in photovoltaics in Poland, it is still wind power plants that have much bigger power (Gram w zielone, 2020). Biogas power plants are also constructed on agricultural land and used for renewable energy purposes. It also needs to be determined whether a selected location of the project will have a negative impact on the network of protected areas NATURA 2000. The negative impact may make the whole procedure much longer.

If the land was purchased after 29 April 2016, it is required to obtain consent of the APA for transferring the dependent possession of the real estate and for carrying out renewable energy investments. The consent is required in the period of 5 years from the date of purchasing the land.

6. Conclusions

Based on the above considerations, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Firstly, under Polish legal regulations the agricultural real estate purchasers are obliged to run an agricultural activity on agricultural land. The obligation refers to the land included in an agricultural farm of an area of at least 1 hectare. There are also provisions regulating changes to the intended use of land and excluding it from agricultural production. Agricultural land, owing to its natural qualities and inevitable process of depletion of its resources, constitutes valuable social good that should be fully and intensively exploited regardless of a type of legal title to it (Stempka-Jaźwińska, 1979, p. 107). It cannot be replaced with any other production means and, therefore, it needs to be prevented from being “worn out” (Błażejczyk M., 1967, p. 78; Wróbel A., 1984, pp. 8-16). Actions taken by the Polish legislator fits into the message coming from European Commission's “farm to fork” strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally friendly food system (F2F) of 20 May 2020.

Secondly, there are regulations pursuant to which the owners and holders have obligations put on them connected with the environmental protection, soil erosion protection, in particular erosion and soil mass movements. The considerations presented in the paper highlight the influence of grassland and feedland on biodiversity. Farmers who cultivate agricultural land in line with sustainable agriculture principles might play a crucial role in biological soil diversity protection. Cultivation tools, techniques and methods influence the land condition (e.g., hedges and grass strips surrounding fields provide for stable habitats and food source for animals that can help to control pest). Farmers apply solutions based on natural environment protection to achieve better results in terms of climate changes and environment protection. Using the EU funds, including direct payments or agricultural, environmental and climatic measures impose obligations relating to environment protection on farmers. Fulfilling those obligations support sustainable agriculture, which is promoted by the European Commission. What needs to be pointed out is that the approach to agricultural land has shifted into the direction of ecological economics, which assumes priority of ecological perspective compared with economics, complemented by the call for intergenerational and intragenerational justice (Biechońska-Goździewicz J., 2018, pp. 41-57). The European Union and Member States, including Poland, have lifted their awareness of the issue of soil (Biechońska-Goździewicz J., 2018, pp. 41-57). Undoubtedly, some further actions need to be taken in the matter.

Thirdly, the legal provisions regulating agricultural land below 1 hectare are more lenient since there is no obligation to run an agricultural activity on that land for 5 years, unless it becomes part of an agricultural farm. The only thing which is not allowed with reference to that land is to sell it or transfer possession of it in the period of 5 years. Some of the land can be used in the future for housing purposes as well as renewable energy or business activity purposes. Such actions contribute to the development of rural areas.

Fourthly, for a few years now there has been a tendency to perform afforestation on the lowest quality agricultural land. Such action is facilitated by the EU funds dedicated for it. There are more and

more private forests every year in Poland, which can be attributed to the schemes in Rural Development Programmes. In the years of 2007–2013, the area of 36.763,15 hectares was afforested.

Fifthly, agricultural land tends to be more often dedicated for renewable energy investments which involve building and maintaining solar power plants or wind farms. Development of renewable power industry in Poland helps to fulfil our international obligations and constitutes a pillar of constitutional principle of sustainable development.

Sixthly, The European Green Deal sets out a comprehensive strategy to tackle climate and environmental problems. Soils play a key role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030 (Bouma, et al., 2019). Soils in particular play a key role in achieving the EU's ambitious 2050 climate neutrality target. As a major carbon sink, soils play an important role in mitigating greenhouse gas emissions. In addition, soils are highly biodiverse (Jeffrey, S., et al., 2010, p. 128, Montanarella & Panagos, 2021, p. 5) included in the new EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2030.

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